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Older Mexican-Americans' help seeking behaviors: The Influence of The Family Regarding Mental

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to explore and describe how the family influences older Mexican-Americans' help seeking behaviors regarding mental health care service utilization along the South Texas-Mexico border. Disparities in access and use of health and mental health services have led Latinos to be disproportionately represented among those most at-risk for chronic health and mental health illnesses and less likely to receive guideline congruent care. Research on mental health service utilization has documented the presence of economic, cultural, and structural barriers that contribute to the underutilization of health services by Latinos. Researchers conducted three focus groups with 25 mental health professionals in the South Texas-Mexico border region. Researchers followed a semi-structured question list and probed for detail from group participants. Kleinman's Explanatory Model (1980) guided the question list. The researchers used ethnographic content analysis to analyze the transcripts. Findings revealed that family members play a significant role in Mexican American older adults' help seeking behaviors and accessing mental health services. Family members played different roles including serving as informants, providing transportation, assisting with discharge planning as well as others.

Keywords: Older Mexican-Americans, Mental Health, Help-seeking Behaviors

1. Introduction

The purpose of this study is to explore and describe the roles of the family and social network that influence Mexican-Americans' help seeking behaviors regarding mental health care service utilization along the South Texas-Mexico border. How do the family and social network influence the help seeking behaviors of older Mexican Americans in South Texas? Disparities in access and use of health and mental health services have led Latinos to be disproportionately represented among those most at-risk for chronic health and mental health illnesses and less likely to receive guideline congruent care. Research on mental health service utilization has documented the presence of economic, cultural, and structural barriers that contribute to the underutilization of health services by Latinos. One element of the Latino culture that is significant is the family and its extended network of immediate and fictive kin; when adults experience mental distress and issues related to aging, the family, and their support network of friends and neighbors assume the responsibilities related to social, emotional, and financial support and caregiving.

2. Literature Review

Latinos diagnosed with mental illness tend to not access or utilize mental health services available to them (Alegria et al, 2008; Blanco et al., 2007; Cook, McGuire, & Miranda, 2007). Alegria et al (2002) examined disparities in utilization rates of specialty mental health care, defined as treatment by a mental health professional such as a psychiatrist, psychologist, or psychotherapist in a specialty mental health setting, and found that a significantly higher proportion of non-Latino Whites (11.8%) received specialty care than African Americans (7.2%) or Latinos (5.9%). Similarly, Miranda and Cooper (2004) found that Latinos were less likely to receive specialty mental health treatment than African Americans or Whites, and that the odds of Latino(a)s receiving any treatment for depression were lower than those for White patients. Disparities in access and use of health and mental health services have led Latinos to be represented disproportionately among those most at-risk for chronic health and mental health illnesses and less likely to receive guideline congruent care compared to non-Hispanic Whites (Blanco et al., 2007; Alegria et al., 2008). Extensive research on mental health service utilization has consistently documented the presence of economic, cultural, and structural barriers that contribute to the underutilization of health services by Latinos compared to the general population and other ethnic groups (Marin, Escobar, & Vega, 2006; Atdjian & Vega, 2005; Vega & Lopez, 2001; Villa & Aranda, 2000).

In line with the documented barriers and disparities to mental health services, a lower number of Mexican Americans participate in the health care arena and are compliant with their medical regimens. More important is the lack of mental health research of Mexican Americans along the South Texas- Mexico border, especially since it is difficult to determine the true extent of mental health needs because there is a

lack of data and information. Research highlights the need for understanding relevant factors that affect positive outcomes and lead to pervasive disparities in mental health service use among this population (Lewis-Fernández, Das, Alfonso, Weissman, & Olfson, 2005).

The U.S. Census Bureau (2012) estimated that Latinos will comprise almost one-third of the U.S. population by 2060. In Texas, the projections have Latinos becoming the majority between 2026 and 2027 with the increase expected to be larger along the Texas–Mexico border (U. S. Census Bureau, 2006; Texas State Data Center, 2006.) Along the border, the poverty rate is approximately 30-35% of the population. This is significant because according to Hudson (2005), people who were impoverished were three times more likely to suffer from a mental illness.

Perhaps no other element of the Latino culture is as significant as the family and its extended network of immediate and fictive kin; thus, *la familia* (the family) includes individuals who are blood related and some in the community that are not blood related. *La familia* is comprised of a nuclear family and an extended network of immediate and fictive members, bound by strong feelings of loyalty, identification, attachment, mutual support, and solidarity among its family members (Gonzalez, German, & Fabrett, 2012; Organista, 2007). When older adults experience mental distress and issues related to aging, the family and their natural support network of friends and neighbors assume the responsibilities related to social, emotional, and financial support and caregiving. This caregiving responsibility, however, is not without its consequences. A strain ensues on the family that is often shared by more than one generation (e.g., the older adult, the adult child, and adolescent grandchildren). In such circumstances, many families' roles and responsibilities may even become interchangeable (Beyene, Becker, & Mayen, 2002; Becker, Beyene, & Mayen, 2003). Adult children change roles with their parents; they become their caregivers while parents become care receivers.

Latinos are often dependent on family support and friends to meet their health care needs (Angel, Angel, McClellan, & Markides, 1996). Keeping physical and emotional problems in the family is a norm that contributes to their reluctance to take advantage of available health care services (Magilvy, Congdon, Martinez, Davis, & Averill, 2000). With respect to mental illness, the issue of mistrust is an added factor. In one study, Schwarzbaum (2004) investigated potential barriers to counseling specifically for Hispanics who were identified as having a low income. Schwarzbaum found Latinos from low-income families were more likely to have a sense of mistrust with non-Hispanic counselors primarily based on fear of being labeled “loco” (crazy) or perhaps running the risk of being deported. In short, family caregiving can be a double-edged sword in times of need for health services. The family can be a great facilitator in helping older Latino family members access needed resources including mental health services, yet at other times, the family can be a barrier to accessing these services.

Specific cultural norms within the Latino community influence decision making about integrating with formal service systems to meet care needs. In particular, the constructs of *familismo* (familism), when not acknowledged and incorporated into the care experience, can affect patient adherence to treatment services as well as outcomes (Barron, Hunter, Mayo, & Willoughby, 2004). *Familismo*, a Latino cultural value, refers to the centrality of a strong family, the loyalty, and closeness that contributes to the welfare of the nuclear family, extended family, and kinship networks (Cauce & Domenech- Rodriguez, 2000; Guilamo-Ramos et al., 2007). Latinos are also more likely to incorporate personal support resources including family in the treatment process, thus, enhancing adherence when the care is perceived positively (Flores, Abreu, Schwartz, & Hill, 2000; Hansen & Aranda, 2012). Family relationships can also serve as a context to support service provider connections and influence decisions about care and functioning to solidify or deter choices to seek and adhere to care as individuals move through the illness experience (Pescosolido, Wright, Alegria, & Vera, 1998; Villatoro, Morales, & Mays, 2014).

The purpose of this study was to explore and describe the roles of the family and social network that influence older Mexican-Americans' help seeking behaviors regarding mental health care service utilization along the South Texas-Mexico border. Understanding these roles will assist mental health care professionals that work with Mexican-Americans in helping families and caregivers to cope with their ill relatives.

3. Methods

The ways in which Mexican-Americans experience mental illness and find meaning for their mental health experiences are best studied using a qualitative approach. Therefore, consistent with Padgett's (1998) recommendations, a focus group qualitative methodological approach was used to study Mexican- Americans' help seeking behavior and the influence of the family when it comes to mental health service utilization. As a first step in studying this hard-to-reach population, researchers decided to seek information from treatment professionals working with Mexican-American clients. The study relied on focus groups to gather practitioners' perceptions of clients' and family mental health treatment experiences.

The researchers recruited 25 mental health practitioners (N = 25) from the South Texas-Mexico border to attend one of three focus groups. The researchers selected mental health practitioners because they have firsthand knowledge of clients' families experience with mental health services. The practitioners were 22 Latinos, 2 Anglo, and 1 Asian-American. The twenty-two Mexican-American practitioners spoke English and Spanish. The practitioners stated that all of their clients spoke English and Spanish. The purpose of the focus groups in which they participated was to generate diverse ideas. For this reason, all members were encouraged to participate. Researchers collected narratives in summer 2016. The researchers held the focus group discussions at three different locations along South Texas- Mexico border: McAllen/Edinburg, Brownsville, and Laredo.

The South Texas-Mexico border is predominantly Mexican-American, and the majority of residents are able to speak English and Spanish; however, some residents speak both languages interchangeably at the same time. The majority of mental health professionals chosen for the study were also bilingual in English and Spanish. In general, focus groups should occur in nonthreatening environments with a group of individuals who share certain characteristics to allow for a good group dynamic and greater self-disclosure (Krueger & Casey, 2000).

After receiving IRB Approval, researchers conducted focus groups in private conference rooms at three agency facilities. The researchers obtained informed consent from all participants in the study. Focus group participants sat around the conference room table and were able to see one another. Two moderators conducted focus groups in the language that the participants preferred (English, Spanish, or a combination of both). Researchers have experience facilitating focus groups. Focus group discussions lasted an average of 60 minutes, and they were recorded for transcription purposes (Krueger & Casey, 2000).

The researchers followed a list of semi-structured guiding questions and probed for examples, clarification, and/or details from group participants. The focus group questions centered on the role of the Mexican-Americans' families in utilizing mental health services. The questions were adapted from Kleinman's explanatory model (1980), which is frequently used to examine help-seeking behaviors and culture.

According to Kleinman, an explanatory model encompasses the notions a person has about an episode of illness and its treatment as delivered by all those who engage in the clinical process. Explanatory models examine people's cognitive processes based on their cultural knowledge and idiosyncratic experiences. Popular culture and the media inform explanatory models, as do the health care culture and the social network of the individual. These elements guide the interpretation and action concerning health. Individuals form explanatory models to cope with a specific health problem. Explanatory models determine what important clinical evidence is, and how it is organized and interpreted for treatment approaches. Explanatory models assist patients and families in making sense of illness episodes (Kleinman, 1980).

Analysis began immediately after the focus group discussions. Researchers did not need to make any adjustments to the guiding questions or research protocol. Researchers performed all the content analysis, including conceptual refinement and identification of pertinent categories. Finally, the researchers integrated and interpreted the study findings. The researchers used ethnographic content analysis (Altheide, 1996; Stark & Roberts, 2005) to analyze the transcripts of the practitioners' perceptions of the role of the family with regard to Mexican Americans mental health treatment use. Ethnographic content analysis centered on the identification of concepts, collection of narratives, and emergent patterns and categories through repeated study of the content or text. Ethnographic content analysis followed a recursive and reflexive movement between the narratives and the interpretation of those narratives by the different members of the research team. The aim was to be systematic and analytic but not rigid. The process was oriented toward clear description and definition. According to Altheide (1996), the process of qualitative document analysis includes examining the content of the narratives to permit emergence, refinement, or collapsing of additional categories.

Ethnographic content analysis enabled researchers to organize the data. Four coders independently coded each transcript one by one with each of the category of family roles. The codes identified keywords, phrases, meanings, and concepts. The authors then met and discussed similarities and potential connections among keywords, phrases, and concepts, within and across the focus groups. Coding discrepancies were reconciled through these discussions. All codes and their meanings are presented in the Findings section per category. This is a descriptive analysis and was not concerned with prevalence of mental distress.

To enhance the trustworthiness of the collected narratives, the researchers also conducted individual interviews with three of the mental health professionals who also participated in the focus groups to provide an opportunity for "member checking." The interviews lasted 30 minutes. Member checking, or returning to the field to verify our analysis, ensures that our interpretation is on the right track (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). In the analytic process, we also engaged in modified member checking with some focus group participants by asking them to explain further any material about which we had questions regarding the meanings and the themes that emerged from the transcriptions/interview recordings.

4. Results

This study was interested in the roles the family plays with a loved one who is involved in mental health treatment. Family members could include husbands, wives, children, in-laws, etc.; however, the one that practitioners identified as being most likely to help was the daughter. Daughters often accompany the family member, and they often encourage the individual to follow through with treatment. They serve as an interpreter of sorts by helping the individual understand the diagnosis and/or treatment.

Researchers identified several roles that the family takes on to help access mental health services including transportation, managing medications, informant, educator, discharge planning, and follow-ups. At times, family members took multiple roles in helping their loved one access mental health treatment. An overarching theme was that family is a part of the treatment team. The families play a significant role in the process of help-seeking and accessing mental health services. Practitioners in one focus group stated, "Part of the treatment team..." The family took on these roles at any stage of the treatment process for their loved one. The family served in these roles for their loved one and for the treatment team. One practitioner reported:

Their son or daughter come in and they're involved in their care; they know exactly what's going on... they know everything -- all the medications she's taking, why she's taking them, what problems she's experiencing and so forth.

Often, family members take on a variety of roles when an individual is seeking help. Some of the main roles identified in this study include informant, educator, and transportation provider. The family helps manage medical treatment by ensuring that regimen is followed. They also help with discharge planning and follow-up. This facilitates the care of the individual because families partake in the process of ensuring that treatment needs of the individual are met.

Daughters/Wives

A second overarching theme that practitioners reported was the daughter or wife being the most instrumental in assisting their loved one in accessing mental health treatment services.

Were instrumental in helping, called the treatment program and encouraged clients to attend, worked with treatment team and went to initial appointments; explained the program to the clients and helped get appointments.

The daughters were the primary caregivers. They helped in each of the family roles that practitioners reported.

Many times, it was daughters, a lot of it falls on the daughters... They're always accompanied by somebody. Their wives or a daughter. Majority of the time, it's a daughter.

Commitment

A significant theme that emerged from the data was the commitment of the family with regard to the identified roles. The family members that serve in these roles as part of the treatment team were supportive. They participate in staffing with the treatment team. They have a strong commitment to their loved one benefiting from treatment services. By attending the meetings, the family helped the treatment team understand their loved one and the family learns about their loved ones' illness.

Family Roles

Transportation

The family was the "primary mode of transportation for these appointments" for several cases. This role was significant because their loved one needed much help particularly with the first step of receiving treatment. The family helping transport their loved ones also supported making the appointments for treatment services and subsequent doctors' appointments. In this role, the family was a significant factor to the continuity of care for their loved one's mental health treatment.

Informant

The family was the informant for the treatment team. The family provided vital information about the patient and the patient's situation. "They were sometimes... the patient maybe doesn't divulge information or share but someone is there they help." Family members also helped the treatment team fill in the gaps of information when needed. Many times, family members helped corroborate the information that clients would provide to the treatment staff, particularly when clients were not always forthcoming. The family helps their loved one overcome the resistance to getting help. They help their loved one navigate the treatment services, including taking medications.

I think the family members realize that the client has an issue, has a problem and they've just have been trying to navigate to get them that help and the patient themselves have been resistant to get that help because they don't want to acknowledge that they have an issue.

The family would often help validate answers to questions that the treatment team had of their loved one.

The family member just jumps in, and they will go ahead and answer the questions when the client is, uh, hesitant to answer or is unsure.

During some assessments on clients, family members provide more information. At times, this information provides a different picture than what the client is describing.

I have also experienced where I have the patient there, and they don't open much but once the family member comes in, it's like you get a whole different picture. So, it can be from one extreme to the other.

Educator

The family members collaborated and helped clarify things for the treatment team and for their loved one. They learned about medications and helped their loved one understand how the medications help. Family members helped explain the treatment services to their loved ones and provided support to help them to continue participating in treatment. Family members help their loved ones understand their prescribed medications. Family members help educate their loved one as well as the treatment team.

Medication management

The family also took on the role of medication management. It is important for the family's loved one to take their medications as part of the treatment services. The family helped make sure that the individual was taking their medications. The family also helped with getting refills so that their loved ones did not run out of medications.

Making sure they, get the medications ...explain something about the medication to the client the family member and they might be involved in getting medication refills

I need a follow up appointment, or I still need to discuss this so you know they will still call us once in a while...just for follow ups or reference to medications that they ran out.

Discharge Planning

The family also takes a role in discharge planning and when looking ahead to see what is next. The family plays a very important role because they provide for or continue to provide some of that education to their loved one and possibly medication management after discharge.

Whether they are going home, or whether they are going to live independently or whether we are looking at nursing home. We need to get the family on board as quickly as possible.

The family made sure that the plan is for their loved one, will be followed through and to follow up with treatment staff.

Follow-up

Along the process of treatment services for their loved one, the family helps make sure that their loved one kept follow-up appointments. The family continued supporting their loved one and supporting the treatment team.

I need a follow up appointment, or I still need to discuss this so you know they will still call us once in a while...just for follow ups or reference to medications that ran out.

5. Discussion

For many Latino families, both nuclear and extended family members tend to play a major role when it comes to making decisions about health and mental health. In this study, the findings were consistent in this aspect. Providers noted that if Latino individuals need to ask for help with mental health issues, they are very likely to rely on their family to not only help them make this decision, but to seek out help and follow through with recommendations.

Family members contribute in a number of ways such as serving as informants. Sometimes the individual seeking help might minimize the symptoms or behaviors that are a concern, and family members are likely to provide additional information about behaviors observed or situations that have created the concern. After seeking help, the family members might be likely to notice changes and/or provide support. This study indicated that daughters/wives are generally primary caregivers and are instrumental in seeking services for their loved ones. In Latino culture as in other cultures, daughters and/wives are often seen as influential individuals in family units to seek appropriate services for their loved ones. Often, family members took on a variety of roles when an individual was seeking help. Some of the main roles identified in this study included: informant, educator, transportation provider. The family ensured the medical treatment regimen was followed. They also help with discharge planning and follow-up.

A limitation of this study is generalizability due to the qualitative nature of the data collection. The study sample was purposive, which makes it difficult to generalize to all Latinos. However, findings do provide insights into the experiences of Mexican-Americans and the associated cultural norm of that community with the mental health treatment experience. Another limitation of this study is the exclusion of those who did not access nor complete the outpatient mental health programs to understand the challenges that families have with getting their loved ones into mental health treatment services. The agencies also did not track individuals who had difficulties accessing the program due to personal factors or decisions about care. These populations would have been ideal for comparisons and will be considered for future studies.

Implications and recommendations

This study gives the South Texas-Mexico border mental health care community insights into the contributors of mental health care utilization for Mexican Americans. These insights will also help the South Texas-Mexico border mental health care community to improve services and service delivery.

Education of mental illness and treatment services

Recommendations for social work and health care providers are to increase education on mental illness and services to Latinos and their families. Providing education will help increase the understanding of mental illness and mental health services. For example, Latinos and their families need education concerning the insurance benefits for which they qualify for mental health services, plus general information about mental health. Another need is to reduce stigma of mental illness and mental health treatment. To do this, we need to provide community education on mental illness and mental health services. There exists confusion of what mental illness is. Today, we understand

that mental illness is a part of life. Targeting young adults will help reduce the stigma of mental illness and provide the opportunity to educate the community about mental illness and mental health services.

Cultural Distance

With the current population growth, the barriers and needs of Latinos will need ongoing assessment. Assisting Latinos to identify the barriers they are experiencing is vital to these assessments. Older adults might not identify a challenge as a barrier. In working with older Latinos, social workers need to consider the degrees of acculturation, language skill and preference, as well as adherence to traditional customs, values, and norms of those being treated (Santiago-Rivera, 1995).

Professionals need to move beyond holding a simplistic view of culture (e.g. creating a physical atmosphere and hiring people who speak the language); to one that incorporates the multiple dimensions of culture in a more detailed way (Bernal & Castro, 1994). For social work professionals, some suggestions for moving beyond a simplistic view of culture include cultural competency training focused on the language and culture of the region. Professionals need to understand and learn that Spanish exists in different dialects, that Latinos come from different countries, and that Latinos have lived different lifestyles and have different life experiences. Understanding the language that older Latinos are using will improve services for both the professional and the patient.

To decrease this cultural distance, planners need to take into account both factors of the linguistic minority clients and the factors of the professionals who will be working with them. Professionals need to understand the cultural distance for each individual client, and to provide accurate assessments. Professionals providing treatment to linguistic minorities need to understand these considerations within themselves to do so effectively. In a pilot study, Choi and Gonzalez (2005) found contributors to access of older minorities included physician social worker referrals, churches, former patients, and community outreach. They also noted having a supportive family, and the treatment agency having bilingual/bicultural clinicians were also contributors (Choi & Gonzalez, 2005).

In social work, we learn to meet the client where they are. In working with older Mexican- Americans, there are times where there exists much cultural distance. Incorporating the value of familismo into services can help decrease this distance. For example, one thing to do for a Mexican- American client who has limited command of English is to translate keywords of the topic that is presented. This helps the Mexican-American client feel respected because the staff took the time to personalize services. This type of service helped respondents commit to the treatment services. Familismo is significant in the culture for older Mexican-Americans. When they find services that are family-like, adherence to prescriptions and treatment recommendations will be more likely. Adding the values of personalismo and respeto to practice makes services feel like family. The services also feel less like western medicine and more like something traditional or something that the older Mexican-American is used to.

Future directions for research

The President's New Freedom Commission on Mental Health (2003), addresses the special mental health needs and strengths of Latinos. One of the most studied reasons for Latinos underutilization of mental health services is the lack of linguistically and culturally relevant services (Lopez, 2002). The design of services for Latinos needs to be relevant to the community where they live. Future research should focus on improving mental health services for Latinos. Services will need to address cultural competency and be linguistically appropriate.

6. Conclusion

Research is needed on how to improve education on mental illness and mental health treatment for the caregivers of Latinos (e.g. their adult children), their health care providers, and the communities in which they reside. Education on mental illness and treatment will help reduce the stigma of mental illness, and improve adherence to treatment Latinos (Gonzalez, 2006). The language that research and treatment programs use is another area in need of research. Professionals and researchers need to understand and learn that Spanish is regional and exists in different dialects. Latinos come from different regions of the United States and emigrate from different countries. Along with linguistic needs, increasing the number of bilingual/bicultural health care providers would improve treatment and research (Gonzalez, 2006).

In addition, future research should focus on attitudinal barriers to the treatment of depression among ethnic minority patients (Cooper et al., 2003). Research on access and retention of minority adults in mental health treatment is also a need (Choi & Gonzalez, 2005). The types of services effective in engaging older Latinos and the value of community supports are two areas of research that could strengthen delivery of mental health services to older Latinos (Brennan, Vega, Garcia, Abad, & Friedman, 2005). To improve the accessibility of services, research needs to be done on culturally competent interventions that are effective with Latinos (Choi & Gonzalez, 2005; Marin et al., 2006). Studies need to focus on improving treatment adherence and on developing methods for engaging patients (Delgado et al., 2006; Choi & Gonzalez, 2005; Marin et al., 2006).

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